

Barriers Hindering Youth from Accessing Youth-Friendly Reproductive Health Services in Iringa Municipality, Tanzania

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to explore barriers that hinder youth from accessing Youth-Friendly Reproductive Health Services (YFRHS) in Iringa Municipality. The study adopted a mixed-methods design, combining both qualitative and quantitative approaches. A sample of 115 participants was drawn, comprising 109 youths, two healthcare providers, two religious leaders, and two ward council leaders. Data were collected through questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions and analysed using thematic analysis and descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that negative attitudes of health providers (71%), stigma and discrimination (69%), lack of confidentiality (63%), and insufficient knowledge (60%) were the most critical barriers. The study concludes that institutional, cultural, and psychosocial barriers significantly restrict youth access to reproductive health services. It recommends strengthening counselling services, staff training, and community engagement to foster supportive and youth-sensitive environments.

Keywords: Barriers, Youth-Friendly Services, Reproductive Health, Counselling Psychology.

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Introduction

Youth-friendly reproductive health services are vital in promoting adolescent wellbeing, preventing unwanted pregnancies, and reducing the prevalence of sexually transmitted infections. However, in Tanzania, young people face multifaceted barriers in accessing these services. Existing literature highlights that judgmental provider attitudes, lack of confidentiality, limited service accessibility, stigma, and structural shortcomings significantly hinder adolescents from seeking care. For instance, Mazur et al.

(2018) found that healthcare workers' moralistic behaviour discourages adolescents, while Habtu et al. (2021) observed that cultural stigma and providers' discomfort create additional challenges in Ethiopia. Similarly, Janighorban et al. (2022) reported that entrenched social stigma and fear of community backlash restrict girls' access in Iran, while Mathabela et al. (2024) emphasized the exclusion faced by adolescents with disabilities in South Africa.

Erikson's psychosocial development theory, particularly the stage of identity versus role

confusion, explains the internal struggles adolescents face when seeking reproductive health services. Adolescents in Iringa Municipality, like many in sub-Saharan Africa, are often caught between societal expectations and personal needs. These findings suggest that barriers are both structural and psychosocial, necessitating interventions that address service delivery and emotional support. Counselling psychology has been identified as an effective approach in reducing stigma, empowering decision-making, and improving health-seeking behaviour. This study therefore integrates empirical evidence and psychosocial theory to explore barriers facing youth in accessing YFRHS.

Empirical studies further strengthen this background. Mazur et al. (2018) highlighted that despite increased policy support, unfriendly provider attitudes and confidentiality concerns persist as global barriers to youth access. Habtu et al. (2021) identified cultural stigma and lack of training among providers as key constraints in Ethiopia. Janighorban et al. (2022) emphasized how entrenched stigma and parental backlash in Iran reduce girls' willingness to seek care. Mathabela et al. (2024) examined youth with disabilities in South Africa, stressing the dual challenges of physical inaccessibility and discriminatory provider attitudes. These findings demonstrate that barriers are widespread across contexts and emphasize the urgency of addressing both structural and psychosocial obstacles. By situating this study within such empirical evidence, it is clear that youth in Iringa Municipality face barriers that mirror global patterns while also reflecting unique cultural dynamics.

Despite national and international commitments to provide youth-friendly services, many young people in Tanzania remain underserved. Iringa Municipality continues to record high HIV prevalence and adolescent pregnancies, pointing to gaps in service access. While facilities exist, negative provider attitudes, inadequate confidentiality, and cultural stigma hinder effective utilization. There is limited empirical evidence that specifically explores how psychosocial and institutional barriers intersect to affect youth access in this setting. This study

addresses that gap by focusing on Iringa Municipality. The study aimed to explore the barriers hindering youth from accessing youth-friendly reproductive health services, identify the psychosocial and institutional challenges that limit access, and provide evidence-based recommendations for improving service accessibility. It was guided by the following research questions: What barriers hinder youth from accessing YFRHS in Iringa Municipality? How do psychosocial and institutional factors influence service accessibility? What strategies can improve youth access to reproductive health services? The study provides valuable insights for policymakers, healthcare providers, and community leaders. It highlights the critical barriers preventing adolescents from utilizing available services and underscores the importance of counselling in addressing psychosocial challenges. Findings will inform interventions aimed at reducing stigma, improving service delivery, and strengthening community support systems.

Materials and Methods

A mixed-methods design was employed, integrating both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The study was conducted in Iringa Municipality, with Gangilonga Ward selected due to its concentration of youth-related institutions and organizations. The population comprised youth aged 15–24, healthcare providers, and community leaders. A total of 115 participants were included. Stratified random sampling was used for youth, while purposive sampling was applied for healthcare providers and leaders. Data collection tools included questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions. Quantitative data were analysed using SPSS, while qualitative data underwent thematic analysis. Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Iringa Ethical Review Board, and confidentiality was maintained throughout.

Results

The youth who participated in the focus group voiced overwhelming concern over how their needs were met with judgment, embarrassment, and silence at both home and facility levels.

One male participant described his experience:

When you enter the health center, you start feeling uncomfortable even before reaching the desk. You can see the nurse watching you as if you're out of place. Some workers make comments like 'what are you looking for at your age?' That one question makes you feel ashamed of even asking anything. It's like they are waiting to humiliate you just for seeking help (Interviewed on 6th May 2025, FGD Participant, Male, 18 years)

Another female participant added:

Sometimes when I go to the clinic, I sit down and my heart beats fast. I'm scared someone I know will see me. Even worse, when the nurse shouts your name and asks you loud questions, everyone around turns to look. That embarrassment is enough to stop me from going again (Interviewed on 6th May 2025, FGD Participant, Female, 20 years)

These views affirm the 71% who cited negative health worker attitudes and the 63% who identified lack of confidentiality as barriers.

Furthermore, several youths highlighted the emotional weight of stigma in their community:

If people see you going to a reproductive health centre, the rumours begin. They will say you are already active or irresponsible. One of my classmates was seen near the centre and within two days, people started calling her names. Even her parents punished her without even knowing the reason she went there (Interviewed on 6th May 2025, FGD Participant, Female, 17 years)

It's worse for boys, too, in another way. People think boys don't need such services. If I try to ask for condoms or counselling, they look at me like I'm a criminal. Even pharmacies are judgmental (Interviewed on 6th May 2025, FGD Participant, Male, 22 years)

This perception aligns with the 69% who reported stigma and discrimination, and the 66% who feared being seen at the facility.

Another consistent concern was inadequate knowledge:

Most of us don't know what reproductive services we are allowed to get. I only found out recently that there is counselling, HIV testing, and family

planning for youth. But no one tells us. We just guess, or rely on what our friends say (Interviewed on 6th May 2025, FGD Participant, Female, 16 years).

When discussing parental involvement, youth described home environments filled with fear and silence:

In my home, even mentioning 'reproductive health' is a taboo. If I bring up anything related to sex or pregnancy, my father says I'm ruining my future. So I end up pretending I don't have questions, but inside I'm confused and scared (Interviewed on 6th May 2025, FGD Participant, Male, and 19 years)

Another female participant said:

My mother once told me that good girls don't talk about such things. So, even when I got my first period, I didn't know what to do. I just stayed quiet and panicked. That's how we live, scared of our own bodies (Interviewed on 6th May 2025, FGD Participant, Female, 15 years)

This elaborates on the 57% who cited lack of parental support, which in turn contributes to reduced awareness and low utilization of services.

Community Leaders' Views

Community leaders acknowledged that youth in their areas face intense social pressure that discourages them from seeking services.

One leader explained:

In our culture, anything related to reproductive health is treated as something secret or shameful. Youth are expected to stay silent. If they ask questions, even their parents suspect them of misbehaviour. So they remain uninformed and vulnerable (Interviewed on 13 May 2025).

He added:

It's not that parents don't care, it's that they are afraid. They fear that talking about these issues gives youth permission to become sexually active. That fear leads to more harm than good.

Another leader emphasized the community's need for education:

We can't keep hiding. When youth get pregnant or get sick, it affects all of us, not just the family.

As leaders, we must change how we talk about these topics and involve parents in the process (Interviewed on 13 May 2025).

Religious Leaders' Views

Religious figures admitted their institutions had previously contributed to stigma, but expressed evolving attitudes.

One religious leader stated:

Yes, in the past we used to preach abstinence without offering any support. But now we are seeing the consequences. Young girls come for prayers after getting pregnant or infected. We realize that silence is not the solution. Reproductive health is not sin it is wisdom (Interviewed, 15 May 2025)

Another added:

The youth need guidance, not punishment. God teaches us to protect life. If we can help a youth prevent disease or delay pregnancy through education, then we are fulfilling a moral duty. But the services must be offered with respect and privacy (Interviewed, 15 May 2025).

Health Care Providers' Views

Health care providers offered crucial insights into the structural and interpersonal challenges affecting youth access to reproductive health services. They acknowledged the presence of judgmental attitudes among some of their colleagues and admitted that such behaviors, whether intentional or not, discouraged youth from seeking services.

One provider candidly stated:

Sometimes we forget that these are still young people nervous, unsure, and afraid. A harsh tone or raised voice can easily shut them down. We don't always get training on how to talk to youth properly (Interviewed, 15 May 2025).

This reflection corresponded with the 71% of surveyed youth who cited negative provider attitudes as a major deterrent. Providers further noted that workload and understaffing contributed to rushed services, making it difficult to maintain confidentiality or build rapport with young clients. One nurse explained:

There are days when we see over 100 patients. Even if a teenager comes, it's hard to give them the attention and privacy they need. We end up serving

everyone the same, and that doesn't work for youth (Interviewed, 15 May 2025).

This operational pressure led to scenarios where youth felt exposed, overheard, or dismissed reinforcing the 63% who reported lack of confidentiality as a barrier. Additionally, providers recognized gaps in adolescent-friendly infrastructure. Many health centres lacked private consultation spaces, waiting areas for youth, or staff trained specifically in youth counselling. A clinical officer remarked:

We've received guidelines on Youth-Friendly Services, but implementation is poor. There's no funding, no dedicated rooms, and sometimes the policies stay on paper. It's frustrating for us and even more for the youth (Interviewed, 16 May 2025)

Another critical point raised was the disconnect between service provision and community engagement. Health workers felt that without support from families, schools, and religious institutions, their efforts were limited in reach and impact. As one provider noted:

We can provide contraceptives or counselling, but if the youth go home and get punished for using them, they won't return. We need the whole community on board (Interviewed, 16 May 2025).

Despite these challenges, health care providers expressed strong interest in improving youth access. They proposed several interventions, including regular training workshops on adolescent communication, establishing youth-only service days, and collaborating with peer educators to bridge trust gaps. One midwife shared:

If we train youth to speak to their peers and refer them, they will come in more confidently. We just need to make the space feel safe (Interviewed, 16 May 2025).

Health care providers acknowledged that judgmental attitudes and lack of confidentiality often discourage youth from accessing reproductive health services. They attributed these challenges to high workloads, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient training in adolescent-friendly care. Providers also emphasized the importance of community support from families, schools, and religious

leaders to enhance service effectiveness. To address these issues, they proposed practical reforms such as peer educator programs, staff training, and creating private, youth-friendly service spaces.

Discussion

The quantitative results indicated that a significant proportion of youth experienced institutional and interpersonal obstacles in accessing YFRHS. The most commonly reported barriers included negative attitudes of healthcare workers (71%), stigma and discrimination (69%), lack of privacy/confidentiality (63%), and insufficient knowledge about services (60%). These findings emphasized that beyond the availability of services, the behaviour and approach of healthcare providers and community members play a vital role in influencing youth decisions to seek reproductive health services. These findings echo Alege *et al.* (2023); Mesiäislehto (2021), who found similar patterns in Uganda and Tanzania, where youth reported feeling excluded by hostile staff and misunderstood by their communities.

Qualitative data from focus group discussions further illuminated the emotional and psychological burden of these barriers. Several participants described feeling scrutinized, embarrassed, and judged by healthcare workers. The act of seeking reproductive services, especially for girls, was perceived as shameful or morally inappropriate. One female participant described being questioned loudly in a waiting room, leading to emotional distress and reluctance to return. These experiences confirmed that provider attitudes directly contribute to the inaccessibility of services, a theme also explored by Nyblade and Stockton (2022), who emphasized the persistent impact of provider stigma across Sub-Saharan Africa.

The fear of being seen at reproductive health facilities was reported by 66% of youth. This fear was rooted in a broader culture of stigma, where community members, including peers and family, perceived visits to these centres as evidence of sexual activity. Participants expressed anxiety over being gossiped about or reprimanded at home, especially if seen by neighbours or schoolmates. This public visibility

acted as a silent deterrent and reinforced avoidance behaviours among youth, just as Nyblade and Stockton (2022) argued that social surveillance and gossip act as invisible policing tools that undermine youth autonomy.

Lack of parental support, reported by 57% of respondents, emerged as both a cultural and generational barrier. Youth described households where topics related to sex, menstruation, or contraception were avoided or outright condemned. This silence created a vacuum of knowledge and support, forcing many adolescents to rely on peers or social media for reproductive health information. The fear of parental judgment further disempowered youth from seeking services, a situation comparable to the intergenerational gaps in communication described by Alege *et al.* (2023).

Another major challenge was the insufficient knowledge and awareness among youth about the existence and scope of available services. Despite the presence of reproductive health centres, many participants admitted they were unaware of what services were offered or whether youth were eligible to access them. Misinformation or lack of information served as an invisible barrier, compounded by limited school-based education on reproductive health. This reinforces the need, as emphasized by both cited authors, for greater community education to normalize youth access.

Structural and logistical constraints such as long waiting times (45%) and limited service hours (38%) were also reported. Many youth, especially those in school or informal employment, found clinic schedules incompatible with their routines. Additionally, health facilities were often crowded or located far from residential areas, making access physically and emotionally exhausting.

The combined effects of these barriers revealed a complex and layered reality. Youth often faced simultaneous challenges: fear of stigma, provider insensitivity, lack of information, and logistical issues (Mesiäislehto, 2021). These obstacles did not exist in isolation but were interrelated, compounding each other's effects. For instance, a youth who feared being judged by a provider might also be afraid of being seen by community

members, leading to total disengagement from services.

The findings demonstrated that youth in Iringa Municipality were not disengaged or uninterested in reproductive health services because they were systematically excluded by an environment that lacked privacy, empathy, and education. Addressing these barriers will require a coordinated response involving healthcare system reforms, community sensitization, parental engagement, and youth empowerment initiatives.

Conclusion

The findings of the study affirmed that youth in Iringa Municipality faced significant and multifaceted barriers in accessing reproductive health services. These barriers operated at multiple levels individual, familial, community, and institutional and were reinforced by cultural taboos, generational communication gaps, and systemic neglect. At the individual level, youth were burdened by the fear of judgment, embarrassment, and shame, which deterred them from openly seeking care. At the family level, discussions around sexuality were often silenced by norms that viewed such topics as inappropriate or immoral for young people, especially unmarried girls.

The health system itself compounded these challenges. Many healthcare workers lacked proper training in adolescent engagement and demonstrated judgmental or dismissive attitudes, making youth feel unwelcome or unsafe. Infrastructure limitations such as the absence of private counseling rooms also undermined confidentiality, causing many youths to avoid services altogether. The result was a generation of adolescents who, despite having physical access to clinics, were emotionally and socially excluded from care. This exclusion had serious implications: it increased vulnerability to unplanned pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), unsafe abortions, and poor mental health outcomes. Addressing these barriers required more than structural fixes; it demanded a cultural shift in how society viewed youth sexuality and a transformation of service delivery to prioritize dignity, privacy, and emotional support.

Recommendation

The findings of this study highlight the need for comprehensive interventions that address both psychosocial and institutional barriers to youth access to reproductive health services in Iringa Municipality. Healthcare providers should undergo continuous training on adolescent-friendly service provision, with a focus on confidentiality, empathy, and non-judgmental communication to reduce negative attitudes and discriminatory practices. Health facilities should be restructured to include private, youth-sensitive spaces that promote confidentiality and trust, while counselling services must be integrated as a core component of youth-friendly reproductive health programs to address internal struggles such as embarrassment, low self-esteem, and fear of stigma. At the community level, awareness campaigns involving parents, teachers, and religious leaders are essential for creating supportive environments that normalize open discussions on reproductive health. Strengthening peer educator programs will further empower young people by offering relatable role models and accurate information. To complement these efforts, the health system should address structural barriers by improving staffing levels, reducing provider workloads, and ensuring adequate infrastructure. Collectively, these strategies can foster a holistic framework that significantly improves access to reproductive health services and enhances the wellbeing of adolescents in Tanzania.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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